

X-Band Electron Paramagnetic Resonance Spectra of Copper(II)-Diglycylglycine (1 : 1) System

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EPR spectra of copper(II)-diglycylglycine (1 : 1) system have been studied at different pH values. A pH-controlled variation in the structure of copper(II)-diglycylglycine complex has been observed.

Copper(II) chelates of amino acids and peptides are used as models for Type-2 copper centres in copper proteins¹. Diglycylglycine(dgG) is a simple peptide with two peptide bonds. It has four potential coordination sites, viz. an amino group, a carboxyl group and two peptide groups. The two peptide groups can act as a O or N⁻ donor under different experimental conditions. The formation of complex of diglycylglycine with copper(II) was first studied by Martell and Kim² using ir and potentiometric methods. We have recently reported formation constants³ and d.m.e. behaviour⁴ of the copper(II)-diglycylglycine system. In the present communication, we report the electron paramagnetic resonance behaviour of this system at different pH values. The results reveal a pH-controlled structural change in the copper(II)-diglycylglycine complex. Such changes have earlier been observed for copper-proteins. In case of stellacyanine, for example, Peisach *et al.*⁵ explained this change in terms of the successive release of certain constraints on the coordination.

Results and Discussion

From the room temperature spectra at different pH values (4.20 – 11.50) it is apparent that there is a continuous change in spectral features as the pH is raised from 4.20 to 8.54. Further rise in pH does not cause any change in the spectral features, although the entire spectrum shows slight rightwards shift (towards higher field). Spectra at pH ≥ 6.75 show nitrogen hyperfine splittings.

In the spectra at liquid nitrogen temperature, two different types of spectra are apparent. At the lowest pH (4.0) of study, the spectrum is characterised by relatively smaller A_{\parallel} (140 G) and larger g_{\parallel} (2.29) values, so that all the four g_{\parallel} lines are obtained before the strong g_{\perp} signal sets in. The spectra at neutral pH (7.15) and onward are characterised by larger A_{\parallel} (~ 210 G) and smaller g_{\parallel} (2.19) values, so much so that $m_I = -3/2$ signal appears beyond the g_{\perp} signal. The spectrum at pH 5.0 shows mixed features. No nitrogen superhyperfine structure is observed either on the parallel or on the perpendicular feature. At low temperatures, when water solutions are frozen, aggregation of

solute molecules occurs, causing broadening of the epr signals due to interaction between neighbouring copper(II) ions⁶⁻⁸.

Martell and Kim² in the pH-metric study of the Cu^{II}-diglycylglycine system worked out the distribution of various species as a function of pH. It would be appropriate to interpret the epr spectra at different pH values on the basis of this distribution curve. We take up the interpretation of the epr spectra in the following two pH groups (taking the higher pH group first for the sake of convenience).

(i) $pH > 7$: At pH 8.54, species 3 (Table 1) is almost exclusively populated, so that the spectrum

TABLE 1—STRUCTURES SUGGESTED BY TWO SCHOOLS FOR VARIOUS SPECIES WITH COPPER(II)-GGGH₂ (1 : 1) SYSTEM

Species	Sarkar's structure ^a	Martell's structure ^b
1		
2		
3		
4		

^aRef. 9.

^bRef. 2.

at this pH is a pure spectrum of species 3. At pH 10.75, species 3 and 4 are almost equally populated, so that epr spectrum at this pH represents the following equilibrium,

It may be noted that the spectra at pH 8.54 and 10.75 are almost identical except that the whole spectrum at higher pH is shifted slightly towards higher field, suggesting that the ligand field strength is increased. An increase in the ligand field is also expected when the coordinated water is deprotonated on increasing the pH. At pH 11.50, population of species 4 increases at the cost of the species 3 and the relative population of species 3 and 4 is nearly 1 : 3. This population change causes further slight shift of the spectrum towards higher field as expected.

At liquid nitrogen temperature also, the epr spectra for all high pH cases are similar, and are characteristic of tetragonal copper(II) with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state $g_1 > g_2$. The g and A tensor values are given in Table 2.

(ii) $pH < 7$: At pH 6.75, the distribution curve shows presence of species 2 and 3 in almost equal population. The epr spectrum at pH 6.75 also appears to be two overlapping quartets (of $I=3/2$ of Cu). The signal on extreme right is clearly due to species 3 as evidenced by nitrogen hyperfine features. At pH 5.5, the system contains free Cu^{II} and species 1 and 2. The spectrum at this pH is not well resolved. At pH 4.2, the system contains mainly free Cu^{II} along with species 1. The spectrum is again broad and partly resolved. The broad and poorly resolved nature of spectrum at low pH is common with the observation of Falk *et al.*⁶, who observed a single broad line at pH 2.4 in their epr study of Cu^{II} -triglycylglycine system. At such low pH the main species suggested to be present is free Cu^{II} ion. This does not account for the observation of a single line broad epr spectrum. Falk *et al.*⁶, offered no interpretation to this unusual observation. We would like to suggest that all copper present in the system at low pH is very weakly bonded to the peptide molecules which at such low pH undergo segregation, so that the Cu^{II} -peptide system becomes abnormally large in size, preventing fast tumbling of the molecules necessary for obtaining resolved four hyperfine line spectra. As the pH is raised the segregation is broken and the four-line hyperfine resolution continuously improves.

At liquid nitrogen temperature even the lowest pH epr spectrum (pH 4.0) is well resolved and is characterised by $g_1=2.29$, $A_1=140$ G and $g_2=2.08$. As the pH is raised, there is systematic change in the parameters reflecting contributions from various species described in the above paragraphs. Values of the g and A tensors are collected in Table 2.

Nitrogen hyperfine lines: Frozen solution (at liquid nitrogen temperature) epr spectra do not

TABLE 2—PARAMAGNETIC RESONANCE SPECTRAL PARAMETERS FOR BINARY COPPER(II)-DIGLYCYLGLYCINE (1 : 1) SYSTEM

System	pH	g_0	$A_0(\text{G})$	$A_1(\text{G})$	g_1	g_2	$A_1(\text{G})$
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{dgG}$ (1 : 1)	4.00	—	—	—	2.29	2.08	140
	4.20	—	—	—	—	—	—
	5.50	2.14	80	42	2.26	2.08	155
	6.75	2.12	82	27	2.20	2.08	193
		2.12	85	31	—	—	—
	7.15	—	—	—	2.19	2.07	210
	8.54	2.11	85	23	2.19	2.07	210
	10.75	2.10	85	22	2.18	2.07	211
	11.50	2.10	85	22	—	—	—

show any hyperfine lines. ^{14}N hyperfine lines are observed in the room temperature isotropic spectra only for the solutions with $pH \geq 6.75$. Throughout ($pH \geq 6.0$) only five hyperfine lines are observed. Structures suggested by Martell and Kim² and Sarkar and Lau⁹ for various species of copper(II)-diglycylglycine complexes are given in Table 1. For the structures suggested for the high pH species, one would expect seven nitrogen hyperfine lines; but only five have been observed. Following alternative structures may be suggested for the two high pH species (3 and 4). These structures account well for the five hyperfine lines and still meet the requirements of the pH-titration results. These

structures have only two equatorially coordinated nitrogens. For the copper(II) systems with the unpaired hole in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital, hyperfine couplings are expected to occur only with the ligand atoms in the plane and not with the axial ligands⁷.

Expansion of the superhyperfine structure reveals that each of the superhyperfine lines is split into doublet. Such splitting of the hyperfine lines into doublets may be due to interaction of the unpaired spin with the proton of the coordinated OH at 10.75 both the species 3 and 4 are in equilibrium, which is apparently so fast that the epr is unable to see the distinction between the two species. Copper(II)-triglycylglycine complex has no coordinated OH, and shows no splitting of superhyperfine line⁶ therefore.

Experimental

Crystalline diglycylglycine (Sigma) was used as such. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. The pH of sample solution was adjusted by adding small quantity of 1M NaOH and 1M

HCl. Copper(II) and peptide were taken in 1:1 ratio. After adjusting the pH to a desired value the solution was allowed to stand at room temperature for at least 10 min before being frozen in liquid nitrogen. The pH values of all solutions were routinely checked both before and after epr experiments and no aging effects were detected.

The epr spectra were measured with a Varian, E-line centuray series spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band with 100 KHz modulation. Solid diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was used as field marker. The samples were introduced in a flat aqueous solution cell to study the epr spectra at room temperature. The frozen samples were placed in a Varian liquid nitrogen insert Dewar flask for measurement at 77 K.

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References

1. T. SAKURAI and A. NAKAHARA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **853**, 847.
2. A. E. MARTEL and M. K. KIM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **91**, 914.
3. K. B. PANDEYA and R. N. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 602.
4. H. L. NIGAM, K. B. PANDEYA and R. N. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
5. J. PRISACH, W. LEVINE and W. BLUMBREG, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1967, **242**, 2847.
6. K. E. FALK, H. C. FREEMAN, T. JANSON, B. G. MULMSTROM and T. VANNGARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 6071.
7. K. E. FALK, E. IVANORA, B. ROOS and T. VANNGARD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 556.
8. R. ROSS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 3919.
9. B. SARKAR and S. J. LAU, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1971, **246**, 5938.